

Comparative evaluation of marginal microleakage of Activa bioactive, Conventional glass ionomer and Composite restorative material: An in vitro study

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Abstract:

Long term adhesion between the restorative material and tooth with minimal microleakage is utmost important for success of restoration. Despite the Continuous evolution of restorative materials- problems such as marginal microleakage is still persisting. Recently, a novel bioactive restorative material, Activa Bioactive Restorative Glass (Pulpdent Corp., Watertown, MA, USA), has been developed claiming to imitate the physical and chemical properties of natural teeth. **Aim:** To evaluate the marginal microleakage of Activa bioactive and to compare it with conventional Glass ionomer and Composite restorative material. **Materials & Method:** In this study, 60 non-

carious premolars extracted for orthodontic purpose were selected and class V cavities were prepared on the buccal surface of teeth. The teeth were then restored as per manufacturer's instructions in the groups assigned. Group A- bioactive restorative material (Activa Bioactive) group B - conventional GIC (GC IX) and group C - composite restorative material (3M Z350XT). The teeth were thermocycled and marginal microleakage was analysed using dye penetration method under a stereomicroscope. **Result:** Total 60% of teeth in group I (Activa Bioactive) were recorded as showing no microleakage (Score 0 - no dye penetration), followed by 50% in group III (Composite resin - 3M Z350XT) and 20% in group II (Conventional GIC- GC IX). Statistically significant microleakage was seen with group II (Conventional GIC- GC IX) ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** All the materials tested in this study had shown microleakage. The highest microleakage was seen with Glass ionomer cement and lowest microleakage was seen with of Activa Bioactive Restorative material which was comparable to composite restorative material.

Key words: Activa Bioactive, Microleakage, Composite resin, Glass ionomer cement

Introduction:

The purpose of restorative dentistry includes removal of diseased hard and soft tissues, and subsequent restoration with an appropriate material to simulate the anatomy, function, and esthetics of a natural tooth. Ideally this material should produce a high-quality seal that is resistant to further ingress of bacteria & oral fluids into the micro spaces between the restoration and tooth causing minimal microleakage. The material should show the long-term adhesion between the restoration and tooth maintaining physical strength of the tooth.¹

Most Commonly used Restorative Materials in dentistry includes silver amalgam, Glass Ionomer Cements and its modifications and Composite Resins & its modifications. Despite the Continuous evolution of materials like resin modified glass ionomer cement (RMGIC), compomers, giomers,

ormocers, zirconomers etc., problems such as marginal microleakage (clinically undetectable passage of bacteria, fluids, molecules, or ions between a cavity wall and the restorative material) still persist.¹

Continuous development of material sciences has resulted in the introduction of bioactive restorative materials in dentistry. The interaction between bioactive materials and living tissue can activate a mechanism for tissue repair or synthesis, inducing the formation of hydroxyapatite. Recently, a novel bioactive restorative material has been developed known as Activa Bioactive Restorative Glass (Pulpdent Corp., Watertown, MA, USA). According to the manufacturer, these bioactive products contain a bioactive ionic resin matrix, shock absorbing resin components, and reactive GI fillers that imitate the physical and chemical properties of natural teeth.² It is an enhanced RMGI with a blend of diurethane monomers modified by the insertion of a hydrogenated polybutadiene (a synthetic rubber) and methacrylate-based monomers. The added resin monomers improve wear resistance, fracture, and marginal chipping. Also include bioactive fillers, which mimic the physical and chemical properties of natural teeth. They actively participate in a dynamic system of ion exchange with the saliva and tooth structure. In addition, they can release and recharge with calcium, phosphate and more fluoride than GIs and continuously react to pH changes in the mouth. They can also form a chemical bond to teeth and seal the cavities against bacterial microleakage.³ According to the manufacturers, Activa bioactive products are strong, esthetic, and long-lasting restorative materials that can replace composites which have the same properties but lack potential bioactive components. They can also replace GIs, which are bioactive but have poor esthetics and poor physical properties. Even after continuous development in restorative materials, microleakage remains a major cause of failure of restorations due to secondary caries, staining of restorations causing tooth discoloration, marginal deterioration, postoperative sensitivity, and

pulpal pathology.⁴ Therefore, the purpose of this in-vitro study is to evaluate the marginal microleakage of Activa bioactive and to compare it with conventional glass ionomer and composite restorative material.

Material & Methods:

A total of 60 non-carious premolars extracted for orthodontic purpose were selected for the study. After cleaning & removing residual organic tissue, teeth were stored in distilled water at room temperature until further use to prevent dehydration. Class V cavities (3mm in length, 2 mm in width, and 2 mm in depth) were prepared using a high-speed airtor hand piece with a cylindrical diamond point on the buccal surface of the teeth. The restored teeth were divided into three groups randomly using a simple randomization technique

- Group I - Bioactive restorative material (Activa Bioactive) (n=20)
- Group II - Conventional GIC (GC IX) (n=20) and
- Group III - Composite restorative material (3M Z350XT) (n=20)

All restorations were performed according to the manufacturer's guidelines.

Group I- Bioactive restorative material (Activa Bioactive)

- After cleaning and drying cavity with a cotton pellet to remove external moisture and avoid complete desiccation, teeth were restored with Activa Bioactive restorative material (Pulpdent® corporation, USA) using an Activa-spenser dispensing gun (Pulpdent® corporation, USA) and light-cured for 20 seconds followed by Glycerin (an oxygen barrier) application for it to self-cure.

Group II - Conventional GIC (GC IX)

- After cleaning and rinsing, cavity was conditioned for 20 seconds using 10% polyacrylic acid (Dentin Conditioner, GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) and rinsed with water for 10 seconds followed by drying with a cotton pellet to avoid complete desiccation. Cavities were restored with freshly mixed conventional GIC restorative material named GC IX restorative (GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). Followed by application of a coat of varnish (GC Fuji VARNISH, GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan).

Group III - Composite restorative material (3M Z350XT)

- After acid etching for 15 seconds using 35% phosphoric acid, the cavities were rinsed with water for 10 seconds and air dried. Dentin bonding agent were applied and light cured for 20 seconds. Teeth were restored with composite restorative material (3M Z350XT) and light cured for 20 seconds followed finishing and polishing of restorations

All the restored teeth were stored in distilled water at room temperature. The restored teeth were subjected to 1000 thermocycles between 5 °C and 55 °C in a water bath with Dwell time of 60 seconds with 10 seconds of transfer time between water baths. Following Thermocycling procedure, the teeth were prepared for the microleakage assessment.

Preparation of the teeth (Specimens) for Microleakage Assessment:

To limit dye penetration to the cavity margins, all tooth surfaces except a one mm wide zone around the margins of the restoration were painted with nail varnish and the teeth apices were sealed using sticky wax. Samples were immersed in 5% methylene blue dye for 24 hours to allow dye penetration along the margins of restorative materials. Each tooth was rinsed, dried and sectioned buccolingually through the center of the restoration with the help of a low-speed water-

cooled diamond disk. The obtained specimens were examined under 40X magnification in a stereomicroscope to evaluate the microleakage.

The degree of microleakage was determined Based on the extent of dye penetration along the cavity walls of the restoration. ⁵

Scoring Criteria

- Score 0—no dye penetration
- Score 1—dye penetration involving half the occlusal/gingival wall
- Score 2—dye penetration involving more than half the occlusal/gingival wall
- Score 3—dye penetration involving the axial wall

An independent investigator did the scoring of all samples to eliminate bias. The microleakage scores were compared for differences using the Kruskal–Wallis test. All testing was done using a ‘p’ value of <0.05. All testing were done using a ‘p’ value of <0.05.

Results:

The total percentage of samples showing microleakage scores of 0, 1, 2, and 3 was 43%, 37%, 13.3%, and 6.7%, respectively. The percentage of samples showing microleakage score 0 was highest for group I (60%) followed by group III (50%) and group II (20%). Microleakage score 1 was seen in 30%, 50%, and 30% of samples of group I, group II, and group III, respectively. Microleakage scores 2 and 3 were seen more in samples of group II, 20% and 10%, respectively. The percentage of samples showing scores 2 and 3 in group I were 10% and 0%, respectively, and that in group III was 10% and 10%, respectively. (FIGURE 1)

Intergroup Comparison

The microleakage scores were compared between the groups using the non-parametric ANOVA test Kruskal–Wallis test. It showed that there is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the microleakage between bioactive and conventional GIC restorative materials & composite and conventional GIC restorative materials. The lowest microleakage was seen with group A restoration. The result of this test showed that the microleakage of group B restoration was statistically different as compared to microleakage shown by group A and group C ($p < 0.05$). It was found that group A and group C restorations did not differ statistically in their microleakage ($p = 0.1820$).

Discussion:

Dental restorative materials have evolved in accordance with technological advancement based on variation in the physical properties and different material constituents, including packability, flowability, diverse insertion techniques (incremental vs bulk), and distinctive restoration delivery methods (thermal and/or sonic energy).⁶ Although unique and user-specific, many of these

restorative materials have shown promising yet contradictory outcomes regarding marginal microleakage.^{7, 8}

Most frequently encountered problem with restorations is the microleakage occurring at the tooth-restoration interface.⁹ Many factors such as insufficient adhesion, polymerization shrinkage, inadequate moisture control, and incomplete removal of the smear layer, are responsible for the formation of marginal gaps between the cavity wall and the restoration.¹⁰ Recently, a novel bioactive restorative material has been developed known as Activa Bioactive Restorative Glass (Pulpdent Corp., Watertown, MA, USA).² Those materials are ionic composite resins which combine the biocompatibility, chemical bond and the ability to release fluoride of GIC with the mechanical properties, aesthetic and durability of RBC.¹¹

In the present study, we have compared the microleakage of the Activa Bioactive restorative with the conventional glass ionomer cement (GC IX, GC India corp.) and light cure composite material (3M z350XT). Several methods are available for detecting microleakage. These include the use of dyes, chemical tracers, and radioactive tracers, neutron activation analysis, and fluid filtration. A dye leakage method was used in this study as it is simple, reliable and well accepted.¹² Among the various dyes available, methylene blue was selected because of its low molecular, which is smaller than the diameter of a dentinal tubule and has the ability to penetrate through the smallest of gaps between the interface of the tooth and restoration.⁶

The results of present study showed that although all the materials showed some form of microleakage, there is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the microleakage between bioactive and conventional GIC restorative materials & composite and conventional GIC restorative materials. The lowest microleakage was seen with Activa Bioactive restoration and highest with GC IX restoration was statistically different ($p < 0.05$). It was found that Activa Bioactive restoration

(Group I) and Composite (3M Z350XT) restoration (Group III) restorations did not differ statistically in their microleakage ($p=0.1820$).

Previously different researchers had studied the marginal microleakage of Activa bioactive and compared it with other restorative materials. No single conclusion could be drawn from the results of these studies. Results of our study that is microleakage in active bioactive restorations are lower or comparable to composite restorations, were in accordance with the studies done by BR Omid *et al.* (2018)³, Jain K *et al.* (2022)⁴, Adeyeye A *et al.* (2023)¹⁴, Pracheth TV *et al.* (2024)¹⁵ and Shihabi S & AL-Monaquel MB (2025)¹⁶. Also there are studies done by Alkudhairy FI & Ahmad ZH (2016)¹³, Owen BM *et al.* (2018)⁶, Tohidkhah S *et al.* (2022)¹⁷, Martínez-Sabio L *et al.* (2023)¹⁸, and Khuva H *et al.* (2024)¹⁹ have found that Activa Bioactive restorations shows greater microleakage compared to the composite restorations. These contradictory results in previous studies for the same material may have resulted from different handling and manipulation of materials.

Conclusion:

Based on the findings of the present study, the following conclusions can be made:

- All restorative materials tested in this in vitro study exhibited some amount of microleakage.
- Conventional GIC (GC IX) showed the highest microleakage.
- No statistical significant difference was found between Activa Bioactive and Composite 3M Z350XT.
- Bioactive restorative material can be used as an effective alternative restorative material for GIC & Composite.

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